
JOURNALIST ON THE LEGAL FIELD OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Journalism in Uzbekistan today is in search of a new model of a democratic type. Why new? What is wrong with the old system? You say! The fact that she lived by stereotypes that hindered not only the development of journalism, but also the country as a whole. Laws and regulations filled with a democratic spirit regarding the activities of media representatives did not work in practice. This led to the fact that the population ceased to trust the press. The ratings of TV programs have decreased, the population has practically stopped reading newspapers and magazines. Radio also ceased to be a source of information. The population was given only news filtered "from above". Literally, a barrier to this was put in 2017 with the coming to power of Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Even from his election program, he paid special attention to the development of the country's information sphere, saying that "it is impossible to imagine a democratic society without freedom of the press, freedom of expression, freedom of choice." He emphasized that "in this area, the most important task is to strengthen economic independence, independence of the media, further introduction of digital information technologies into their activities, and increase the level of professional training of journalists."

One of the first transformations carried out by the current head of state in the field of reforming domestic television can rightfully be considered the presidential decree of May 2, 2017 "On the creation and organization of the information and analytical TV channel" O`ZBEKISTON 24 ". This decision was made in order to fully realize the potential of the information services of the TV and radio channels and to form an active citizenship among the population and a sense of ownership of the ongoing reforms.

The activities of the new channel are aimed at timely and reliable coverage of events taking place in the country and abroad, their impartial and objective assessment, aimed primarily at meeting the needs of the population in obtaining a

high-quality information product and preventing the spread of unreliable, politically biased and other destructive information and ideologies from outside.

Among the many tasks of the TV channel, there is also assistance in establishing an open direct dialogue between responsible heads of state bodies and organizations with the population, the wide involvement of observers, representatives of the expert community and academic circles to discuss and solve urgent problems of citizens and topical issues on the ground.

Today, the TV channel "O`ZBEKISTON 24" is the central news channel, promptly providing reliable information to all of Uzbekistan. I remember how, before starting to work on this channel, and generally thinking about journalism, it was a good tradition to watch the Akhborot newscast almost every day. It seemed that the presenters of this program are the standard of beauty, style and impeccable diction. Later, having become part of a large team of professionals, experts in their field, I realized what kind of tetanic work they overcame and continue to overcome in order to convey one piece of news to the viewer. It would seem that a 2- or 3-minute story, but how much work has been invested in it, how many people have worked hard so that the facts and news invested in it see the light. The specifics of the channel, like many other state ones, and the informational format require skill and dexterity from the journalist. Sometimes it seems to me that it is much easier to make a 5-6 minute story than 2-3, to squeeze out the most "delicious", as my former editorial colleague Olga Rusakova said, I would say the right thing.

Speaking about the legal field of a journalist, I can say from my own experience that today many of my colleagues work based on the letter of the law. In electronic and printed publications, topics that are vital for the inhabitants of the country are raised. And the very attitude towards journalists has changed. Of course, there are still echoes of the period when journalists worked strictly on orders from above, but now the time itself requires courageous, truthful and impartial media representatives. This does not mean that you must always go ahead, I think you need to keep in touch with representatives of the press services of various organizations, ministries and departments, work together, exchange information, invite heads and employees of these very state institutions for interviews, but not allow them, in any way, to influence the presentation of facts by journalists, in their favor. Again, based on my relatively short work experience and my colleagues who have achieved significant results in their field, I want to say that the support of President Sh. Miramonovich, provided to us journalists of Uzbekistan, gives motivation to work even more diligently and selflessly. Now if a journalist asks the right, correct questions, tries to find true facts, whether he is a

minister, hokim or other high-ranking official, he will not only provide answers to questions, but, as they say, take off his hat. Was it like this in our country some 7-8 years ago? Definitely not."According to the theory of social responsibility, the government not only must allow freedom, but also must actively develop it, with its practical monopoly on physical force is the only factor strong enough to ensure the effectiveness of freedom." Isn't this what we can observe in Uzbekistan now?

Another striking example of the fact that the transformations taking place in the country have reached a high level is the adoption of the updated Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The current version replaced the Constitution approved on December 8, 1992. The new version of the country's basic law was supported by 90.2% of voters. Such an indicator of population activity is really impressive.

What is the reason for making such an important decision? There are many reasons for this. It is paramount that certain articles of the Constitution in the old version did not actually show their effectiveness, many of them simply lost their significance, and additions were made to others.

27 new articles have been added to the updated Constitution, as a result, their number has grown from 128 to 155. Amendments have been made to 65% of the articles of the Constitution. Among the changes are an increase in the term of office of the President of Uzbekistan from five to seven years, a ban on the extradition of a citizen of the republic to another state, consolidation of the principle of direct action of the Constitution, a ban on the death penalty, and much more. Let's look at what changes relate to the activities of media representatives in Uzbekistan. In order to ensure the equal activities of journalists, who are the main sources of reliable information for society, it is necessary to create a solid legislative framework for this. The laws that apply to the activities of media representatives provide, among other things, for the protection of their freedom of speech and the right to disseminate information.

Thus, in the new Constitution, Articles 81 and 82 provide for norms regulating relations between the state, citizens and media representatives.

Article 81

The media are free and operate in accordance with the law. The state guarantees the freedom of activity of the mass media, the exercise of their right to seek, receive, use and disseminate information. The media are responsible for the accuracy of the information they provide.

Article 82

Censorship is not allowed. Obstruction of activities or interference in the activities of mass media shall entail liability in accordance with the law.

Let's turn to international practice. In different countries, legislation reflects different approaches to protecting the integrity and freedom of professional activity of journalists. In the United States, for example, the First Amendment to the Constitution guarantees freedom of speech, including freedom of the press. "Congress shall make no laws concerning the establishment of a religion, or forbidding the free exercise of it, or restricting the freedom of speech or the press, or the right of the people to assemble peacefully and petition the government for the satisfaction of grievances."

In international law, interference in the professional activities of journalists is considered an unlawful violation of freedom of expression and freedom of the press. This is also spelled out in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

Thus, the norms spelled out and supplemented in the new Constitution of Uzbekistan state that any interference in the professional activities of media representatives, whether it is a ban on publishing or expressing one's opinion, is unacceptable and should be suppressed by law. In case of violation, liability is established in accordance with the law. These norms allow journalists to receive protection in case of violation of their rights.

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